

**THE PRINCIPLES OF LEXICAL SEMANTIC ANALYSES OF VERBAL
PHRASEOLOGY (ON THE BASE OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE)**

*S. Sharipova*¹

Abstract:

The article dwells on the analysis on semantic components on the base of lexical definitions and produces semantic features due to which phraseological units are included into the certain group in the general field of movement.

Key words: phraseological unit, lexis, semantic analysis, semantic field, semantic group

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The analysis on semantic components on the base of lexical definitions can be used for the general and a range of differentiated features due to which linguistic units are included into certain semantic groups. The analysis on definitions gave us possibility to underline the basic semantic component of phraseological unit (PhU), included into the field and the group with the semantics of movement. This component of movement expresses the idea of motion that is common for both semantic field and the group.

From lexical definitions we also obtained basic semantic features, due to which phraseological units are included into a certain group in the general field of movement:

1. The feature of directed movement:
 - a) The movement onward: along, forward, towards, ahead, on, forth;
 - b) The movement astern: back, backwards;
 - c) The movement upwards: up;
 - d) The movement down: headlong, downwards;
 - e) The movement in different directions: about, round, in a circle, from place to place;
 - f) The feature of approaching: nearer, insight, into view, at;
 - g) The feature of remove: away, out, out of sight, outdoors.
2. The means of movement: on foot, on a horse, on a train, on board a ship, by road, on horseback, be frequent changes of horses.
3. The speed of movement:
 - a) Fast movement: hurriedly, in a hurry, at great speed, rapidly, hastily, quickly, at full speed, with increasing speed, at top speed, fast, extremely fast, swiftly, at the top of one's speed;
 - b) Slow movement: (very) slowly, at a crawl;
 - c) Cadent movement: at an equal speed.
4. Characteristics of movement:

¹ *Sharipova Sabinabonu, Student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

a) According to quality: without trouble, at once, completely, lively, briskly, suddenly, idly, with great caution, secretly, hastily, without permission or notice, without warning, steadily, by effort, as a dog, narrowly, furiously, vigorously, straight, swimmingly;

b) According to the place of movement: behind, in front, first at back, in close competition, closely after (upon), at the heels.

5. Pointing at the parts of the face: the arm, the head, the body, the legs, feet, heels.

Semantic characteristics, obtained with the help of analysis of lexical definitions, give us a chance to imagine phrase-semantic field of movement in the range of the majority of various semantic groups, which are also divided into certain theme groups and subgroups, synonymic rows, etc.

There is an invariant feature in the base of division of the semantic field into notional groups, i.e. the idea of physical movement and differentiated features such as concrete forms of movement that distinguish one group from another. However, the division is complicated by the fact that the same linguistic unit during the figurative use can be added to another group.

That is why the division of semantic groups has to be done according to the principles of commensurability of criteria of definitions. Thus, we divided phraseological units of movement into semantic groups due to the basic meaning of PhU, given in phraseological dictionaries.

Another type of semantic relations in the field is the relations of phraseological units, the basic feature of which is antonymy, besides similarity: to put in an appearance – to make one's exit, to lead the way – to follow in somebody's footsteps, to go at a crawl – to burn the wind.

The following type of semantic relations in the field is the polysemy. Phraseological units as well as the words, reflect the life in its variety of its relations and dialectic contradiction of phenomenon. Phraseological units are mostly mono-semantic, but even they are able to have several meanings. Especially it is often met in the secondary reconsideration (metaphorical, metonymic) and all the meanings of the phraseological unit can be imagined as a set of interconnected notional components according to the level of abstraction.

Thus, PhU 'to go to the pace' with the meaning 'to hurtle', being reconsidered got the new meaning as 'to live brightly'; PhU 'to mark time' firstly meant only military march, and now possesses a figurative meaning 'to do nothing', 'to waste time'. Here we notice the abstraction from the initial meaning though the connection with it not fully lost. Sometimes the word-combination can be reconsidered several times and, in this case, obtains a range of imagery meanings. Polysemy (plurality of meanings of phraseological units) leads to their ability to join different semantic fields, that is why it is almost impossible to show the precise borders between them.

The principle of similarity and contrast of the meanings of PhU within the field creates the three-level organization of semantic relations, which reflects the real connections of linguistic phenomenon.

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